

COMPATIBILITY STUDIES OF CHLORHEXIDINE WITH PHARMACEUTICAL EXCIPIENTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GEL NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Chlorhexidine is a synthetic cationic bis-biguanide compound used as a topical antiseptic. It is classified as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent with potent bactericidal and bacteriostatic activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Emulgel, combining the hydrophilic properties of gels with the biphasic structure of emulsions, offer enhanced solubility, stability, controlled release, and mucosal penetration. Additionally, Gels further offer ease of application, high spreadability, and good patient acceptability. Clove oil, a natural analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial agent, also improves taste, promoting better compliance. The main objective of the present study was to the preformulation studies were performed to know the development of formulation and evaluation of Chlorhexidine Hydrogel and Emulgel NDDS for topical application. In the present study that the compatibility was assessed by, FTIR spectroscopy and preformulation parameters. Results showed that physical mixtures of Chlorhexidine and various excipients such as Carbopol,

Xanthan Gum as gelling agents. Methylparaben and propylparaben served as preservatives, while propylene glycol, glycerin, Sucralose, Triethanolamine, Clove oil and Tween were evaluated for preformulation studies parameters. It was concluded that the drug Chlorhexidine was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for the formulation development of the Chlorhexidine Hydrogel and Emulgel NDDS. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the ADDS (Advanced Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

KEYWORDS: Chlorhexidine, NDDS, Compatibility, Excipients, Development, Preformulation, Hydrogel, Emulgel.

INTRODUCTION

Bacterial Infections^[1-12]

Bacterial infections often result from the accumulation of bacteria due to poor oral hygiene, leading to gum inflammation, plaque formation, and exacerbation of decay issues. For this reason, Chlorhexidine is considered a disinfectant that helps reduce the number of bacteria and cleanse the oral cavities and it's a broad-spectrum biocide. It is effective against Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria and fungi. The bactericidal effect is a result of the binding of this cationic molecule to negatively charged bacterial cell walls. At low concentrations of chlorhexidine, this results in a bacteriostatic effect; at high concentrations, membrane disruption results in cell death.

Chlorhexidine has a broader spectrum of activity and a faster kill rate than other antimicrobials. Chlorhexidine kills by disrupting the cell membrane and the antifungal activity in the Chlorhexidine. The mechanism of action for fungi is very similar to that of bacteria. *Candida* species is the most common of the fungi present in both healthy and affected individuals. Fungi have been found in the infected root canals that have not had any previous endodontic treatment. The fungus uptakes Chlorhexidine in a short amount of time and impairs the integrity of the cell wall and the plasma membrane entering the cytoplasm resulting in leakage of cell contents and cell death. Oral herpes is a common, recurrent condition marked by painful mucosal lesions and risk of secondary bacterial infections. The treatment combines Acyclovir to combat viral infections and Chlorhexidine to manage bacterial infections, comprehensively targeting both causes while maintaining oral health and minimizing complications.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths^[13-47]

Pharmaceutical research is characterized by having both a natural source and synthetic source for primary active raw materials and excipients, each source is mainly prepared to the effectiveness and safety of the drug.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths include: Pharmacognosy deals with natural sources of drug, Pharmaceutical Chemistry specializes in synthetic sources of drug, Pharmaceutics specializes in designing of pharmaceutical dosage forms and drug delivery systems from natural and synthetic sources of active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients that help in developing dosage forms and drug delivery systems.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths link steps are manufacturing and development of drug according to the standard parameters evaluation such as physiochemical properties, preformulation, formulation, evaluation, drug stability, Pharmaceutical analysis, pre-clinical, post-clinical stages, pre-marketing, post-marketing, Pharmacovigilance, Pharmacoeconomics, Pharmacy Management, Pharmacology, Toxicology, Therapeutics, Pharmaceutical Care, Health Care, Advanced Industrial Pharmacy, Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics, Advanced Clinical Pharmacokinetics, Pharmaceuticals Cosmetics, Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Drug Design, Pharmacy Law and Ethics, Pharmacogenomics, Good Manufacturing Practice, and Good Pharmacy Practice etc.

All of these Pharmaceutical Research Paths are interconnected, and whenever the link between them is made in a scientific relationship and the goal of pharmaceutical care is achieved gradually according to plan of a scientific pharmaceutical research path.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths are the scientific methods through which the scientific relationship between the pharmaceutical team, research, supervisor or specialist researcher, the scientific research materials, equipment's, scientific institution, pharmaceutical companies, reference standards, and the goals of pharmaceutical research improve and development of community services of pharmaceutical care and health care.

Pharmaceutical Scientists are considering natural sources and medicinal herbs in the pharmaceutical industry an important part of drug development because natural sources of drugs have properties that are greater than industrial sources of drugs in NDDS. And the pharmaceutical industry strategies depend on the development of different pharmaceutical

dosage forms and recent novel drug delivery systems. Using medicinal herbs and natural sources as important goals of drug development. It is part of the art of innovation in drug development with different of novel drug delivery systems and pharmaceutical care for patients and society, it's the basic of development of the new pharmaceutical industry by developing different novel drug delivery systems from different sources.

Compatibility Studies^[48-110]

Preformulation is essentials of pharmaceutical science that utilizes biopharmaceutical principles in the determination of physicochemical properties of the drug substance. Prior to the development of any dosage form new drug, it is essential that certain fundamental physical and chemical properties of drug powder are determined. This information may dictate many of subsequent event and approaches in formulation development. The safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the preformulation stage. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the ADDS (Advanced Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

One of the objectives of this study is to development of drug delivery systems by building scientific pharmaceutical research information depend on formulation scientists to join the knowledge and experience as well as experimental and practical results of this study with regard to information in previous studies, and approved references. It was found to be that the most important concepts and basics of preformulation studies such as definitions, methods, conclusion, idea, and types of pharmaceutical analysis techniques using in evaluation of preformulation studies parameters, in this study that we focused on developing drug delivery systems and linking the formulation development to establish the basics of pharmaceutical research in studying the drug-excipient compatibility, dug with various excipients, which is important for the safety, effectiveness, quality, formulation, stability, bioavailability, and pharmacokinetics of the drug etc.

Determination of physical chemical properties of API substance with the goal of developing a new drug which is safe stable and efficacious, each API, has intrinsic chemical and physical properties that were considered prior to the development of pharmaceutical formulation, the purpose of preformulation study is to generate useful information for the formulator in the

development of stable and bioavailable dosage form, inappropriate preformulation study results in poor stability of active ingredients increase the overall cost of development and increased development time, preformulation studies help to fortify the pharmaceutical scientific foundation of the guidance, provide regulatory relief and conserve resources in the drug development and evaluation process, enhance public safety standards, improve product quality, promote the implementation of new technologies, aids policy development and regulatory decision making and after compiling all data it is transferred to the development pharmacist and for the day work on formulation of dosage form.

Preformulation Study Objectives: To establish the Physico-chemical parameters of a new API entity, determine its kinetics and stability, establish its compatibility with common excipients, it provides insights into how drug products should be processed and stored to ensure their quality, estimate problem may arise during formulation that is stability problem poor *in-vivo* dissolution, poor bioavailability, to interpret BCS classification of drugs and its significance and develop optimal drug delivery system.

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Study: The primary objective of this investigation was to identify a stable storage condition for API in solid state and identification of compatible excipients for its formulation. Incompatibilities are major concerns in formulation development. Selection of the proper excipient during preformulation studies is of prime importance.

Dosage Forms: DF contain API and pharmaceutical excipients, which are intended to generate an ideal formulation and manufacturability of pharmaceutical products, thereby enabling a much safer and more effective administration. Pharmaceutical excipients are ideally inactive and have no impact on the stability or therapeutic effect of the active ingredient. On the other hand, there are studies that have presented that some pharmaceutical excipients are just allegedly described as inactive ingredient. Some pharmaceutical excipients have the capacity to affect API, efficacy by affecting its pharmacokinetics. Excipients can affect the physical and chemical form of pharmaceuticals by several factors such as hydrogen bond interaction, polymorphic conversion, and others. Accordingly, drug-excipient compatibility should be conducted so as to determine any drug-excipient interactions that may obstruct the stability, bioavailability, and manufacturability of pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Importance of Drug-Excipient Compatibility

Studies of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API)-excipient compatibility represent an important study in the preformulation stage of the development of new dosage forms, stability of the dosage form can be maximized, any physical or chemical interaction between API, and excipient can affect bioavailability and stability of drug, it helps to avoid the surprise problem, by performing drug excipient compatibility studies (DECS) we can know the possible reaction before formulating final dosage form, DECS data is essential for IND (investigational new drug) submission, and now, USFDA has made it compulsory to submit DECS data for any new coming formulation before its approval.

The potential physical and chemical interactions between an API, and the excipients can affect the chemical nature, the stability and bioavailability of the former and, consequently, its therapeutic efficacy and safety, solid dosage forms are generally less stable than their API components and despite the importance of API-excipient compatibility testing, there is no universally accepted protocol to assess such interactions.

Pharmaceutical Excipients: Excipients are additive substances used to improve the bulkiness, disintegration, dissolution rate, and bioavailability of a formulation etc. Different dosage forms like powders, granules, capsules, tablets, oral liquids, injectable products, implants, eye products, nasal products, inhalers, topical creams, ointments, gels, transdermal patches and suppositories etc, contains different types of excipients. To make it acceptable and compatible various pharmaceutical excipients are added in pharmaceutical dosage form for their direct therapeutic action, manufacturing process, to protect, support or enhance stability, for bioavailability or patient compliance. These must be physiologically and chemically stable, must not have any incompatibility with the API, and must meet the standards of regulatory requirements.

Evaluation of Drug-Excipient Compatibility

The compatibility study of API and excipients is important to predict the stability of the API, in the final pharmaceutical product. It's the first time that API was compatible with excipients promoted physical and chemical compatibility studies was achieved by thermal and non-thermal methods. As a part of preformulation study, a compatibility study of API with the other excipients was carried out using physical blends in analytical techniques for the evaluation of drug-excipient interactions. The most commonly used pharmaceutical analytical techniques include, thermal techniques such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC),

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Isothermal Microcalorimetry (IMC) and Hot stage microscopy (HSM) etc, and non-thermal techniques such as UV-Visible Spectrophotometric (UV), Infrared, Near-Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy (FT-IR), (NIR), Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), Solid-State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (ssNMR), Microscopic techniques: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Chromatographic techniques: Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) etc.

Preformulation Parameters: According to dosage form of API, mainly solid state, particle size, shape, pKa, pH determination, common ion effect, temperature, partition coefficient, solubility studies, dissolution rate, melting point, powder flow properties, crystallinity, polymorphism, hygroscopicity, stability study and drug-excipient compatibility etc. While other dosage forms according to important of preformulation parameters used in study before start in development of formulation.

Drug-excipient compatibility and formulation stability is not depended on API only but also its affected by excipient. Excipient play important role in dosage form but side by side it also increases compatibility problem so proper selection of excipient is very important in development of formulation. Incompatibility can be result mainly in any of following changes: Changes in organoleptic properties, changes in dissolution performance, decrease in potency, and increase in degradation rate etc.

Drug excipient physicochemical characterization is a systematic approach towards design of therapeutically active and stable dosage forms. The rapid advancements in novel drug delivery systems development have led to an interest by formulation scientists in the role and functionality of the excipients.

In the present study, it was proposed to Chlorhexidine -excipient compatibility studies of the safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the preformulation stage, with commonly different excipients using for formulation development of Chlorhexidine Hydrogel and Emulgel NDDS for topical application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chlorhexidine and all raw materials used in the formulation including active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), excipients, and analytical reagents gift from (Global Pharma Pharmaceutical Industry Company - Yemen).

As shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Materials Used.

NO	Name of Materials
1	Chlorhexidine
2	Clove Oil
3	Carbopol
4	Xanthan Gum
5	Methylparaben
6	Propylparaben
7	Glycerin
8	Propylene Glycol
9	Tween 80
10	Sucralose
11	Triethanolamine

Equipment

All equipment used are listed in Table Error! No text of specified style in document.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.: List of Instruments.

NO	Instruments
1	Chamber 40 °C
2	FTIR Spectrophotometer
3	UV-VIS Spectrophotometer
4	Sc Chemtech Ultrasonic Bath
5	pH Meter
6	Brookfield Viscometer
7	Magnetic Stirrer
8	Electronic Balance
9	Digital Thermostatic Water Bath

Evaluation of Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies Methods^[81-169]

Table 3: Chlorhexidine Data.

Chlorhexidine Structure and 3D Conformer

Chemical Structure	(1E)-2-[6-[[amino-[(E)-amino-(4-chloroanilino)methylidene]amino]methylidene]amino]hexyl]-1-[amino-(4-chloroanilino)methylidene]guanidine	Appearance	White, crystalline solid.
Chemical Formula	$C_{34}H_{54}Cl_2N_{10}O_{14}$	Drug Solubility	Solubility: Soluble in dilute acids, acetone, and ethanol; very slightly soluble in water 800 mg/L (at 20 °C). Melting Point: 134-136 °C.
Molecular Weight	897.8 g/mol	BCS	Class-II Drug
Drug Action and Use	<p>Chlorhexidine is a cationic bis-biguanide antiseptic possessing broad- spectrum antimicrobial efficacy against Gram- positive and Gram- negative bacteria, yeasts, and enveloped viruses. Its activity is concentration- dependent: at 0.02 – 0.06 % (w/v) Chlorhexidine exhibits predominantly bacteriostatic properties, whereas concentrations ≥ 0.12 % confer bactericidal effects.</p> <p>Chlorhexidine is a synthetic cationic bis-biguanide compound used as a topical antiseptic. These are molecules containing two p-chlorophenyl rings and two biguanide functional groups linked by a central hexamethylene bridge. It is classified as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent with potent bactericidal and bacteriostatic activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.</p> <p>Chlorhexidine exerts its antimicrobial effects through electrostatic interactions between its positively charged guanidinium moieties and the negatively charged phosphate groups of microbial cell membranes. At bacteriostatic concentrations, this interaction increases membrane permeability, resulting in efflux of</p>		

	intracellular ions such as potassium and phosphate, thereby arresting cellular growth. At bactericidal concentrations, Chlorhexidine penetrates the cytoplasm, precipitates cytoplasmic proteins, and disrupts essential enzymatic systems, ultimately leading to irreversible membrane collapse and microbial cell death.		
Chlorhexidine Pharmacokinetics			
Drug Absorption	<p>Topically, it is unlikely that Chlorhexidine undergoes any degree of systemic absorption.</p> <p>When administered orally, such as in a dental rinse, Chlorhexidine is very poorly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Following a 300mg oral dose in human subjects, the C_{max} was 0.206 µg/l, which occurred at a T_{max} of approximately 30 minutes after ingestion.</p>	Drug Distribution	<p>Volume of Distribution: Chlorhexidine binds extensively to proteins and mucosal surfaces, which limits its distribution into systemic circulation.</p> <p>Protein binding: Chlorhexidine is known to bind to albumin in both serum and saliva, although the specific extent of this binding is not clear.</p>
Drug Metabolism	<p>As Chlorhexidine is very poorly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract, it is unlikely to undergo metabolic conversion to any significant extent.</p>	Drug Excretion	<p>Route of Elimination: Excretion of Chlorhexidine gluconate occurs almost exclusively via the feces, accounting for approximately 90% of an ingested dose. Less than 1% is excreted in the urine.</p> <p>Clearance: Not available. Systemic clearance is not a relevant parameter due to the drug's poor systemic absorption.</p>
The Elimination Half-Life	<p>The elimination half-life of systemically absorbed Chlorhexidine is approximately 5–6 hours. However, due to its substantivity</p>	Availability	<p>Preparations of Chlorhexidine that are available:</p>

(T1/2)	(prolonged local retention) on mucosal surfaces, its antimicrobial activity persists for 8–12 hours post-application.		Orally: Oral solution: 0.12%, Chip: 2.5mg Sugar-free Chewing Gum Toothpastes: 0.12 % Mouthrinses: 0.12 % , 0.2 % Varnishes Topical: liquid/foam: 0.75%, 2%, 4%, Lotion: 1%, Swab: 3.15%, Swab-sticks: 2%, 3.15%, Solution: 2%, Towelette: 0.5% plus isopropyl alcohol 70%/5mL, Sponge: 2%, 4%. Others: Gels: 0.12 %, 0.2 %, 1 % Sprays: 0.1 %–0.2 %
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Table 4: Pharmaceutical Excipients Data.

Incompatibilities	Functional Category	Synonyms	Nonproprietary Name
<p>Carbomers are discolored by resorcinol and are incompatible with phenol, cationic polymers, strong acids, and high levels of electrolytes.</p> <p>Trace levels of iron and other transition metals can catalytically degrade carbomer dispersions.</p> <p>Certain amino-functional actives form complexes with carbomer; often this can be prevented by adjusting the pH of the dispersion and/or the solubility parameter by using appropriate alcohols and polyols. Carbomers also form pH-dependent complexes with certain</p>	<p>Bioadhesive material; controlled-release agent; emulsifying agent; emulsion stabilizer; rheology modifier; stabilizing agent; suspending agent; tablet binder.</p>	<p>Acrypol; Acritamer; acrylic acid polymer; carbomera; Carbopol; carboxy polymethylene; polyacrylic acid; carboxyvinyl polymer; Pemulen; Tego Carbomer.</p>	<p>Carbomers</p>

polymeric excipients. Adjustment of pH and/or solubility parameter can also work in this situation.			
<p>Strong Oxidizing Agents: Can react violently.</p> <p>iron: May cause discoloration.</p> <p>Zinc Oxide: Potential for chemical interaction.</p> <p>Certain Plastics/Rubber: Can degrade these materials.</p> <p>Highly Acidic/Basic Substances: May alter its composition</p>	<p>Analgesic & Anesthetic: Relieves toothaches (eugenol as a local anesthetic). Soothes muscle and joint pain.</p> <p>Antimicrobial: Combats bacteria, viruses, and fungi. Used in oral hygiene products.</p> <p>Anti-inflammatory: Reduces inflammation and swelling. Treats skin irritations.</p> <p>Antioxidant: Protects cells from free radical damage.</p> <p>Antiseptic: Disinfects minor wounds.</p> <p>Dental Applications: Alleviates dental pain, treats gingivitis, and disinfects cavities.</p> <p>Skincare: Addresses acne and purifies skin.</p> <p>Aromatherapy: Provides stimulating and invigorating effects.</p>	<p>Clove bud oil. <i>Eugenia aromatica</i> bud oil. <i>Eugenia caryophyllata</i> bud oil; <i>Caryophyllii floris aetheroleum</i>; Clove volatile oil</p>	<p>Clove Oil</p>
<p>Incompatible with cationic surfactants, polymers, and preservatives, often leading to precipitation, and at concentrations exceeding 15% w/v, anionic and</p>	<p>Gelling agent; stabilizing agent; suspending agent; sustained-release agent; viscosity-increasing agent.</p>	<p>Corn sugar gum; E415; Grindsted; Keldent; Keltrol; polysaccharide B-1459; Rhodicare S; Rhodigel; Vanzan NF; xanthani gummi; Xantural.</p>	<p>Xanthan Gum</p>

amphoteric surfactants can also precipitate xanthan gum from solution. It is incompatible with oxidizing agents, some tablet film coatings, carboxymethylcellulose sodium, dried aluminum hydroxide gel, and certain active pharmaceutical ingredients.			
Glycerin may explode if mixed with strong oxidizing agents such as chromium trioxide, potassium chlorate, or potassium permanganate. Black discoloration of glycerin occurs in the presence of light or on contact with zinc oxide or basic bismuth nitrate. An iron contaminant in glycerin is responsible for the darkening in color of mixtures containing phenols, salicylates, and tannin. Glycerin forms a boric acid complex, glyceroboric acid, that is a stronger acid than boric acid.	Antimicrobial preservative; emollient; humectant; plasticizer; solvent; sweetening agent; tonicity agent	Croderol; E422; glycerine; Glycon G-100; Kemstrene; Optim Pricerine; 1,2,3-propanetriol; trihydroxypropane glycerol	Glycerin
	Sweetening agent	Splenda; sucralosa; sucralosum; SucraPlus; TGS; 10,40,60-trichlorogalactosucrose; 4,10,60-trichloro-4,10,60-trideoxy-galactosucrose	Sucralose
Propylene glycol is incompatible with oxidizing reagents such as potassium permanganate	Antimicrobial, preservative, disinfectant, humectant, plasticizer, solvent, stabilizing agent, water miscible cosolvent.	1,2-dihydroxypropane, E1520, 2-hydroxypropanol; methylethyleneglycol, methyl glycol, propane-1,2diol, propylglycol.	Propylene glycol
Incompatible with alkalis, heavy metal salts, phenols, tannic acid.	Emulsifying agent for the preparation of stable oil-in-water emulsions.	Monolaurates, polyoxyethylene sorbitan, polysorbate	Tween 80

Triethanolamine will react with mineral acids to form crystalline salts and esters. With the higher fatty acids-copper to form complex salts- with reagents such as thionyl chloride.	Alkalizing agent, emulsifying agent, pH adjuster.	Tea, Tealan, triethylolamine, trihydroxytriethylamine , tris (hydroxyethyl)amine , trolaminum.	Triethanolamine
Methyl paraben can undergo hydrolysis under acidic conditions, resulting in the formation of p-hydroxybenzoic acid. Methyl paraben may react with oxidizing agents, such as hydrogen peroxide, and lose its effectiveness as a preservative. Methyl paraben can form complexes with certain metal ions, such as aluminum and iron.	Preservative.	Methyl ester of p-hydroxybenzoic acid, Methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate, Nipagin M, Methyl parahydroxybenzoate, Methyl parahydroxybenzoic acid, Methyl chemosept, MPB, Metoxyguard, Tegosept M, Methyl-p-hydroxybenzoate.	Methylparaben
Magnesium aluminum silicate, magnesium trisilicate, yellow iron oxide, and ultra- marine blue have also been reported to absorb propylparaben	preservatives.	Propyl p-hydroxybenzoate, Propylparaben, E216 (E-number used in food additives), Propyl ester of p-hydroxybenzoic acid	Propyl Paraben
In pharmaceutical formulations, water can react with drugs and other excipients that are susceptible to hydrolysis (decomposition in the presence of water or moisture) at ambient and elevated temperatures. Water can react violently with alkali metals and rapidly with alkaline metals and their oxides, such as calcium oxide and magnesium oxide. Water also reacts with anhydrous salts to form hydrates of various compositions, and with certain organic materials and calcium carbide.	solvent	Filtered water, Distilled water, Deionized water, Purified H ₂ O, Clear water, Pure water, clean water, Pristine water, Crystal-clear water, Treated water	Purified water

According to Chlorhexidine and excipients data as shown in Tables 3 and 4, it was selected that the different excipients to preformulation study with Chlorhexidine in the present study,

Drug Identification Tests

Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) were evaluated by assessing color, odor, and using standardized sensory methods: Color: A small quantity of Chlorhexidine was placed on butter paper and examined under well-illuminated conditions to determine its color characteristics. Odor: A minimal amount of the sample was used to assess its odor through direct sensory evaluation.

UV-Vis Spectrophotometer Analysis of Chlorhexidine

A standard solution of Chlorhexidine hydrochloride was prepared in purified water at 10 µg/ml. UV–Vis spectra were recorded under identical instrument settings and scan range, with baseline correction against purified water. Chlorohexidine di-gluconate in water are exhibits two maxima around 231 and 255 nm.

Calibration Curve of Chlorhexidine

1 ml of chlorhexidine was accurately measured and diluted to 1000 ml with purified water in a 1000 ml volumetric flask to obtain a stock solution (200 µg/ml). An aliquot of 15 ml was taken from the stock solution and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, then the volume was made up to 100 ml with purified water to obtain a concentration of 30 µg/ml. From this solution, 25 ml aliquots were successively transferred to 50 ml volumetric flasks and diluted to volume with purified water to prepare a series of standard solutions with concentrations of 15 µg/ml, 7.5 µg/ml, 3.75 µg/mL, and 1.875 µg/ml. The absorbance of these solutions was measured at 254.5 nm against a blank of purified water. The calibration curve was plotted between concentration and absorbance.

Pre-Formulation Study

A stage of development during which the physicochemical properties of the drug substance are characterized and established. A complete knowledge of the relevant therapeutic and physicochemical properties of the drug enables determination of its proper formulation and delivery method. Preformulation study is to develop the elegant (stable, effective, and safe) dosage form by establishing kinetic rate profile, compatibility with the other ingredients and establish physico-chemical parameter of new drug substance.

Drug and Excipients Compatibility Study

FTIR Spectroscopy Study

IR study was aimed to study the compatibility of excipients with Chlorhexidine in room condition. Each excipient was mixed with Chlorhexidine in equal amounts, then from each sample a small amount was taken (approx 1:1 %) and mixed with about 100 mg of potassium bromide. The KBr- sample mixtures were grinded separately for each sample using agate mortar and pestle. The grinded powders were compressed into discs under pressure of about 10000 pounds per square inch. The tablets were mounted in IR compartment and analyzed. The infrared spectra of the drug - excipient mixtures were recorded over a wave number of 4000 cm^{-1} to 500 cm^{-1} . On analysis of the IR spectra of the reference spectra given in British Pharmacopoeia and pure drug, no major differences were observed in the characteristic absorption peak pattern as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: The Drug and Excipients Compatibility Studies.

Sample Code	Drug with Excipients	Ratio (Drug: Excipient)
1	Chlorhexidine	1
2	Chlorhexidine + Clove Oil	1:1
3	Chlorhexidine + PG	1:1
4	Chlorhexidine + Tween 80	1:1
5	Chlorhexidine + Triethanolamine	1:1
7	Chlorhexidine + Sucralose	1:1
8	Chlorhexidine + Glycerin	1:1
9	Chlorhexidine + Xanthan Gum	1:1
10	Chlorhexidine + Carbopol	1:1
11	Chlorhexidine + Methyl Parapan	1:1
12	Chlorhexidine + Propyl Parapan	1:1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Drug Identification Tests

Organoleptic properties

The organoleptic properties of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) were evaluated by assessing color, odor, and using standardized sensory methods. Results are presented for Chlorhexidine as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Organoleptic Properties of Chlorhexidine.

Tests	Specifications	Observations
Appearance	Colorless to pale yellow, clear, viscous liquid	Colorless, clear, viscous liquid
Odor	Faint, characteristic medicinal odor	Faint, characteristic medicinal odor

Characterization of Chlorhexidine by UV Spectroscopy

UV Scanning of Chlorhexidine in Purified Water

10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Chlorhexidine solution was analyzed under identical experimental conditions as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**. The spectrum exhibited two characteristic absorption peaks: a primary λ_{max} at 254.5 nm and a secondary peak at 231.5 nm. The observed λ_{max} value aligns with the documented two maxima around 231.5 and 254.5 nm for Chlorhexidine.

Fig. 1: Wavelength of Chlorhexidine in UV Spectrophotometer.

Calibration curve of Chlorhexidine in Purified Water

The experimentally determined λ_{max} values were used for subsequent quantitative analyses, including the construction of calibration curves and the determination of drug content in the

prepared formulations. The calibration curve was plotted between concentration and absorbance as shown in Table 7, and Figure 2.

Table 7: Calibration Curve Results of Chlorhexidine in Purified Water.

SN	Concentration	Absorbance	SD
1	1.875	0.0884	0.0001
2	3.75	0.1804	0.0003
3	7.5	0.2637	0.0002
4	15	0.4819	0.0002
5	30	1.0111	0.0001

Fig. 2: Calibration Curve of Chlorhexidine in Purified Water.

Excipient and Drug Compatibility Study

Characterization of Chlorhexidine by FTIR

FTIR spectrum studies indicated that major functional groups present in Chlorhexidine show characteristic peaks in IR spectrum. Figures (3) to (13) show peaks observed at different wave numbers and the functional group associated with these peaks for drug and drug with different excipients. The major peaks are identical to functional group of Chlorhexidine. Hence, it was confirmed that there was compatibility between drug and various excipients, thus conforming that no interaction of drug occurred with the components of the formulation excipients.

Fig. 3: FTIR Spectra of Pure Chlorhexidine STD Fresh and Stored.

Fig. 4: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Clove Oil.

Fig. 5: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Glycerin.

Fig. 6: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Propylene Glycol (PG).

Fig. 7: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Tween 80.

Fig. 8: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Xanthan Gum.

Fig. 9: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Carbomer.

Fig. 10: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Triethanolamine.

Fig. 11: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Sucralose.

Fig. 12: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Methylparaben.

Fig. 13: FTIR Spectra of Chlorhexidine with Propylparaben.

DISCUSSION

The Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of pure Chlorhexidine and its physical mixtures with various excipients were analyzed to assess their physicochemical compatibility. The FTIR spectrum of pure Chlorhexidine exhibits a broad N–H stretching absorption between 3350 and 3200 cm^{-1} , consistent with its biguanide functionality. Aromatic C–H stretches appear at 3100–3000 cm^{-1} , with weaker aliphatic C–H absorptions at 2950–2850 cm^{-1} . A strong, complex vibrational band is observed near 1640 cm^{-1} , arising from coupled aromatic C=C stretching and N–H bending modes. These characteristic peaks

define the spectral fingerprint of Chlorhexidine and provide the basis for evaluating potential interactions. The absorption regions exhibited in the spectrum of fresh Chlorhexidine as shown in Figure 3.

The mixture with clove oil (**Error! Reference source not found.**) showed a pronounced broadening of the 3350–3200 cm^{-1} envelope due to the overlapping phenolic O–H stretch from the oil. Despite this, all of chlorhexidine's core absorptions remained at their original positions, indicating full compatibility.

Similar observations were made for the polyol excipients, glycerin (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and propylene glycol (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The spectra of both mixtures were dominated by the exceptionally broad and intense O–H stretching absorptions characteristic of these excipients, which completely enveloped the drug's N–H region. Nevertheless, a critical examination of the fingerprint region in both analyses confirmed that the integrity of the drug was maintained, with its primary diagnostic peaks remaining present at their original wavenumbers. This demonstrates an absence of chemical interaction and confirms the compatibility of chlorhexidine with both glycerin and propylene glycol.

The evaluation with Tween (**Error! Reference source not found.**) also showed the appearance of a characteristic excipient peak, a sharp ester carbonyl (C=O) absorption at approximately 1735 cm^{-1} . The presence of this peak did not alter the diagnostic fingerprint of Chlorhexidine, whose key vibrational bands remained clearly resolved and unshifted, confirming compatibility.

More complex spectral changes were observed with the polymeric gelling agents. In the mixture with xanthan gum (**Error! Reference source not found.**), a key diagnostic band of Chlorhexidine remained identifiable but exhibited a minor shift and significant broadening. A similar effect was noted in the mixture with Carbopol (**Error! Reference source not found.**), where the same diagnostic band was observed to broaden and overlap with a strong absorption from the polymer. For both gelling agents, these spectral changes, coupled with extensive broadening in the O–H/N–H region, are characteristic of strong, non-covalent associations. These physical interactions are attributed to the formation of an extensive hydrogen-bonded network between the drug and the polymer matrices. Therefore, these observations confirm the physicochemical compatibility of Chlorhexidine with both xanthan gum and Carbopol.

In physical mixtures with excipients such as triethanolamine, sucralose, methylparaben, and propylparaben (Figures 10-13), the resulting spectra were found to be a simple additive superposition of the individual components. The diagnostic Chlorhexidine band near 1640 cm^{-1} and its associated fingerprint peaks remained unaltered in position and intensity, confirming the absence of any significant chemical interaction.

It was concluded that the comprehensive FTIR analysis revealed no evidence of new covalent bond formation or chemical degradation of Chlorhexidine in any of the tested mixtures. Therefore, chlorhexidine was found to be physiochemically compatible with all evaluated excipients under the tested conditions.

CONCLUSION

The compatibility studies of physical mixtures of Chlorhexidine with different used excipients such as Carbopol, Xanthan Gum as gelling agents. Methylparaben and propylparaben served as preservatives, while propylene glycol, glycerin, Sucralose, Triethanolamine, Clove oil and Tween were evaluated for preformulation studies parameters were investigated by FTIR it was detected that there was no variation or minor deviation in the characteristic peaks in FTIR spectroscopy. It was concluded that the drug Chlorhexidine was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for the formulation development of the Chlorhexidine Hydrogel and Emulgel NDDS. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the ADDS (Advanced Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

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REFERENCES

1. Brunton L, B Knollmann, Goodman and Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics, 14th Edition. McGraw Hill LLC, 2022.
2. McDonnell G, AD. Russell, Antiseptics and disinfectants: activity, action, and resistance. Clinical microbiology reviews, 1999; 12(1): 147-179.

3. Mohammadi Z, P Abbott. The properties and applications of chlorhexidine in endodontics. *International endodontic journal*, 2009; 42(4): 288-302.
4. Bobichon H, P Bouchet. Action of chlorhexidine on budding *Candida albicans*: scanning and transmission electron microscopic study. *Mycopathologia*, 1987; 100(1): 27-35.
5. Zeng P, A Rao, T Wiedmann, W Bowles. Solubility Properties of Chlorhexidine Salts. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*, 2008; 35: 172-176.
6. Pillai SGP, Johnson L, Bagde H. Chlorhexidine mouthwash in dentistry. *Journal of Nursing Research*, 2023; 3(3): 24-29.
7. Karpiński TM, AK Szkaradkiewicz. Chlorhexidine--pharmaco-biological activity and application. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*, 2015; 19(7): 1321-1326.
8. Sharp G, S Green, M Rose. Chlorhexidine-induced anaphylaxis in surgical patients: a review of the literature. *ANZ J Surg*, 2016; 86(4): 237-243.
9. Balagopal S, R Arjunker. Chlorhexidine: The gold standard antiplaque agent. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2013; 5(12): 270-274.
10. Taghizadeh F, E Fakhari. Effect of Chlorhexidine Containing Fluoride on Dental Plaque, Gingivitis, and Tooth Discoloration: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Avicenna Journal of Dental Research*, 2021; 13: 67-71.
11. Fini A, V Bergamante, GC Ceschel. Mucoadhesive gels designed for the controlled release of chlorhexidine in the oral cavity. *Pharmaceutics*, 2011; 3(4): 665-679.
12. Fiorillo L. Chlorhexidine Gel Use in the Oral District: A Systematic Review. *Gels*, 2019; 5(2).
13. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, AlGhoury ABA, Alkhawlani MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of *Grewia Tenax* Extract Naturaceutical Ointment for Antimicrobial Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(7): 413-426.
14. Alburyhi MM, Raweh SM, Al-Ghorafi MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of *Argemone Ochroleuca* Extract Cream Naturaceutical Delivery Systems as Antimicrobial and Wound Healing Activity. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(7): 445-459.
15. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Sulfadoxine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(9): 189-207.
16. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Cosmeceutical Natural Pigmented Lipstick from *Opuntia Dillenii* Fruit Extract. *European*

- Journal of Biomedical Pharmaceutical and Medical Sciences, 2025; 12(9): 466-479.
17. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Almlhani AN, Alqadhi AA. Innovative Approaches in Herbal Drug Delivery Systems Enhancing Efficacy and Reducing Side Effects. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 14(1): 919-929.
 18. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Al-Wajih AM, Alqadhi AA, Almlhani AN. Advancements in Nano- Formulation Systems for Enhancing the Delivery of Herbal Ingredients. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(1): 212-231.
 19. Alburyhi MM, Moharram BA. Formulation and Evaluation of Aloe Niebuhriana Extract as Naturaceutical Effervescent Granules Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Antidiabetic Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(18): 1147-1175.
 20. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Novel Antiaging Cream Containing Dragon's Blood Extract. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(1): 239-244.
 21. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Almaktari AM. Formulation and Evaluation of Trimetazidine Hydrochloride and Clopidogrel Bisulphate Multi-unit Solid Dosage Forms. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research*, 2014; 6(2): 421-426.
 22. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Formulation and Stability Studies Evaluation of the Selected Captopril Mouth Dissolving Tablets MDTs. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(11): 275-284.
 23. Alburyhi MM, Moharram BA. Formulation and Evaluation of Jatropha Variegata Extract as Antibacterial Naturaceutical Cream Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Wound Healing Activity. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(10): 177-190.
 24. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Skin Whitening Naturaceutical Composition Gel as Advanced Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(10): 400-414.
 25. Al-Samawi HM, El-Shaibany A, Alburyhi MM. Review Article: The Therapeutic Potential of Micromeria Biflora: A Comprehensive Review. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(6): 7-11.
 26. Alburyhi MM, Moharram BA. Formulation and Evaluation of Aloe Inermis Extract for Wound Healing Activity as Antibacterial Naturaceutical Cream Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(10): 297-308.
 27. Al-Wajih AM, El-Shaibany A, Alburyhi MM, Abdelkhalek AS, Elaasser MM, Raslan AE. Comparative Study of Phytochemical Composition, Oral Toxicity, Antioxidant, and

- Anticancer Activities of Both *Aloe Vera* and *Aloe Vacillans* (Asphodelaceae Family) Flowers Extract: *In Vitro*, *In Vivo*, and in Silico Studies. *Trends in Phytochemical Research*, 2025; 9(1): 1-22.
28. Al-Samawi HM, El-Shaibany A, Alburyhi MM. Review Article: The Pharmacological Potential of The Genus *Micromeria*. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(6): 1-6.
29. Al-Samawi HM, El-Shaibany A, Abdelkhalek AS, Alburyhi MM, Elaasser MM, Raslan AE. Metabolite Profiling and Toxicity, Antioxidant, and Antitumor Evaluation of *Micromeria Biflora* Aerial Parts Extract Combined with ADMET Prediction and Molecular Docking Analysis. *Chemistry & Biodiversity*, 2025; 0: e202403258: 1-19.
30. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Effect of Chewing Khat on Nutritional Status Among Female Students at Undergraduate Level in Sana'a, Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(20): 75-88.
31. Al-Samawi HM, El-Shaibany A, Alburyhi MM. Review Article: Phytochemistry and Pharmacological Activities of *Micromeria* Species. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(15): 1335-1347.
32. Al-Ghani AM, Alkhawlani MA, Alburyhi MM, Alwosabi A. Formulation and Evaluation of Yemeni *Zizyphus Spina-Christi* Leaves Extracts as Anti-Bacterial and Anti-Dandruff Serum. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(10): 40-46.
33. Mohamed YAS, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Alkhawlani MA, Alburyhi MM. Phytochemical and Physicochemical Analysis of Yemeni *Kalanchoe Marmorata* Baker. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 14(9): 1024-1033.
34. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding the Proper Use, Risks and Resistance of Antibiotics Among Undergraduate Level Medical and Health Sciences Students in Sana'a, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(12): 414-425.
35. Almamari A, Alburyhi MM, Alhag S. Species-Species Prevalence of Vaginal Candidiasis with Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Among Women in Sana'a City. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2013; 5(8): 217-224.
36. El-Shaibany A, Alburyhi MM, Aoun MA, Ghallab HA. Pharmacological Evaluation of Marine Macroalgae from Yemeni Coastal Waters: Expanded Investigation into Their Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Activities. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(13): 1763-1770.
37. Al-Ghani AM, Alkhawlani MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation Evaluation of Effect of

- Yemeni *Allium Sativum* (Garlic) in Treatment of Oral Candidiasis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(8): 14-19.
38. Noman MA, Saif AA, Alburyhi MM. The Impact of Vitamin D Deficiency and Nutritional Habits on Height and Health Among Yemeni Adult Female Students in Sana'a, Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2026; 15(3): 855-875.
39. Raweh SM, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Gel of *Azadirachta Indica* Extract Herbal Product. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(2): 427-433.
40. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Capsicum Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Tonic and Natural Stimulant. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(6): 323-337.
41. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Formulation and Evaluation of Captopril Mouth Dissolving Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(1): 18-28.
42. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Alemad AF. Dispersible and Orodispersible Tablets Delivery Systems for Antibacterials Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(1): 1229-1257.
43. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA. Knowledge and Perception about Pharmacovigilance Among 4Th and 5Th Levels Pharmacy Students in Some Public and Private Universities, Sana'a Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023; 9(11): 14-19.
44. Othman AM, Alburyhi MM, Al-Hadad GH. Captopril-Excipient Preformulation Studies for Mouth Dissolving Tablets Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(10): 1398-1420.
45. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Comparative Study of Certain Commercially Available Brands of Paracetamol Tablets in Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2018; 5(12): 36-42.
46. Al Ghoury AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Patterns of *Staphylococcus Aureus* to Different Antimicrobial Agents Isolated as Clinical Samples at Certain General Hospitals in Sana'a City, Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(16): 35-47.
47. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude,

- and Practice of Pharmacovigilance Among Pharmacists and Health care Professionals in Four Government Hospitals at Sana'a City, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(5): 250-267.
48. Nehal SM, Garima G, Pramod KS. Fast Dissolving Tablets: Preparation, Characterization and Evaluation: an Overview. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.*, 2015; 31(2): 243-250.
 49. Deshmukh H, Chandrashekhara S, Nagesh C, Murade A, Usgaunkar S. Superdisintegrants: a Recent Investigation and Current Approach. *Asian J Pharm Tech*, 2012; 2: 19-25.
 50. Abha, Kaur LP. Superdisintegrations: an Arising Exemplar in Orodispersible Tablets. *Int J Drug Res Technol.*, 2015; 5(1): 1-12.
 51. Borse LB, Bendale AR, Borse SL, Naphade VD, Jadhav AG. Formulation and Evaluation of Mouth Dissolving Tablet Rivaroxaban and its Validation. *Biosci Biotechnol Res Asia*, 2022; 19(4): 943-954.
 52. Stuart BH. *Infrared Spectroscopy: Fundamentals and Applications*. 1st ed. Wiley, 2004; S168.
 53. Bharate SS, Bharate SB, Bajaj AN. Interactions and Incompatibilities of Pharmaceutical Excipients with Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients: A Comprehensive Review. *J Excip Food Chem.*, 2010; 1: 3-26.
 54. Moyano MA, Broussalis AM, Segall A. Thermal Analysis of Lipoic Acid and Evaluation of the Compatibility with Excipients. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2010; 99: 631-637.
 55. Ceresole R, Han Y, Rosasco MA, Orelli LR, Segall AI. Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies in Binary Mixtures of Avobenzone. *J Cosmet Sci.* 2013; 64: 317-328.
 56. Chadha R, Bhandari S. Drug–Excipient Compatibility Screening—Role of Thermoanalytical and Spectroscopic Techniques. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 2014; 87: 82-97.
 57. O'Neill MA, Gaisford S. Application and Use of Isothermal Calorimetry in Pharmaceutical Development. *Int J Pharm.*, 2011; 417: 83-93.
 58. Ferraz Pinto M, Afonso de Moura E, Santos de Souza F, Oliveira Macêdo R. Thermal Compatibility Studies of Nitroimidazoles and Excipients. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2010; 102: 323-329.
 59. Oliveira Santos AF, Basilio Jr ID, Souza FS, Medeiros AFD, Ferraz Pinto M, de Santana DP. Application of Thermal Analysis of Binary Mixtures with Metformin. *J Therm. Anal Cal.*, 2008; 93: 361-364.

60. Chou YP, Huang JY, Tseng JM, Cheng Y, Shu CM. Reaction Hazard Analysis for The Thermal Decomposition of Cumene Hydroperoxide in The Presence of Sodium Hydroxide. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2008; 93: 275-280.
61. Mura P, Furlanetto S, Cirri M, Maestrelli F, Marras AM, Pinzauti S. Optimization of Glibenclamide Tablet Composition Through the Combined Use of Differential Scanning Calorimetry and D-Optimal Mixture Experimental Design. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 2005; 37: 65-71.
62. Araújo AAS, Storpirtis S, Mercuri LP, Carvalho FMS, dos Santos Filho M, Matos JR. Thermal Analysis of The Antirretroviral zidovudine (AZT) and Evaluation of The Compatibility with Excipients Used in Solid Dosage Forms. *Int J Pharm*, 2003; 260: 303-314.
63. Matos APS, Costa JS, Boniatti J, Seiceira RC, Pitaluga Jr A, Oliveira DL, Visçosa AL, Holandino C. Compatibility Study Between Diazepam and Tablet Excipients. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2017; 127: A1675-1682.
64. Liltorp K, Larsen TG, Willumsen B, Holm R. Solid State Compatibility Studies with Tablet Excipients Using Non Thermal Methods. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 2011; 55: 424-428.
65. Verma RK, Garg S. Selection of Excipients for Extended-Release Formulations of Glipizide Through Drug–Excipient Compatibility Testing. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 2005; 38: 633-644.
66. Verma RK, Garg S. Compatibility Studies between Isosorbide Mononitrate and Selected Excipients Used in The Development of Extended-Release Formulations. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.*, 2004; 35: 449-458.
67. Veiga A, Oliveira PR, Bernardi LS, Mendes C, Silva MAS, Sangoi MS, Janissek PR, Murakami FS. Solid-State Compatibility Studies of A Drug Without Melting Point. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2018; 131: 3201-3209.
68. Rus LM, Tomuta I, Iuga C, Maier C, Kacso I, Borodi G, Bratu I, Bojita M. Compatibility Studies of Indapamide/Pharmaceutical Excipients Used in Tablet Preformulation. *Farmacia*, 2012; 60: 92-101.
69. Tomassetti M, Catalani A, Rossi V, Vecchio S. Thermal Analysis Study of The Interactions between Acetaminophen and Excipients in Solid Dosage Forms and in Some Binary Mixtures. *J Pharm Biomed Anal*, 2005; 35: 949-955.
70. Ding T, Chen L, Zhai LH, Fu Y, Wang-Sun B. Compatibility Study of Rivaroxaban and Its Pharmaceutical Excipients. *J Therm Anal Cal.*, 2017; 130: 1569-1573.

71. Raymond C. R, Sheskey PJ, Owen CS. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients Fifth Edition Edited.
72. Shivangi S, Navneet V. Taste Masked Orodispersible Tablets. A highly patient Compliant Dosage Form. Asian J Pharm Clin Res., 2016; 9: 385-91.
73. Anupam R. Orodispersible Tablets: A Review. Asian J Pharm Clin Res., 2016; 9: 19-26.
74. Abdelbary G, Eouani C, Prinderre P, Joachim J, Reynier J, Piccerelle P. Determination of The Invitro Disintegration Profile of Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets and Correlation with Oral Disintegration. Int J Pharm., 2005; 292: 29–41.
75. Anusha P, Nirajana A, Mohammed S, Jilani S, Murali C, Harish G. Development and Evaluation of Drotaverine Taste Masked Tablets with Improved Dissolution Efficiency Using Soild Dispersion Technique. IJRPB, 2013; 1: 275–80.
76. Srikanth M, Uhumwangho M, Sunil S, Sreenivasa N, Ravi C, Ramana Murthy K. Design and Revaluation of Taste Masked Drotaverine HCl Orodispersible Tablets Using Polymethacrylate Polymers. Der Pharmacia Lett., 2010; 2: 223–31.
77. Narasimhulu et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Orodispersible Drotaverine Sublingual Tablets. Indo American Journal of Pharm Sciences, 2014; 1(06).
78. Rele RV, Ruparel DG. UV Spent to Photo Metric Estimation of Drotaverine Hydrochloride by Derivative Method in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. International Journal of ChemTech Research, 2018; aa(10): 353-360.
79. Shirwaikar AC. Galan Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Famotidine by Dry Granulation Method. Ind J Pharm Sci., 2004; 66: 422-426.
80. Venkateswarlu B, et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Famotidine Fast Dissolving Tablets by Direct Compression Method. Indian Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Biotechnology, 2013; 9-10(609): 609-613.
81. Sunada H, Bi YX. Preparation, Evaluation and Optimization of Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets. Powder Technol., 2002; 188–198.
82. <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB00878>.
83. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Chlorhexidine>.
84. Reddy RA, Ramesh B. Kishan V. Drug-Excipient Interaction During Formulation Development In -Vitro and In -Vivo Evaluation of Gastroretentive Drug Delivery System for Nizatidine. Int J Pharm Sci Nanotech, 2013; 6: 2281-2293.
85. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Lamotrigine. Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University, 2009.

86. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abudunia A, Yassin SH, Abdullah JH. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Amoxicillin Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(7): 183-197.
87. Alburyhi MM, Salim YA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Furosemide-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(22): 1178-1219.
88. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Lornoxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Microsponge-Based Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(4): 70-81.
89. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Natural Herbal Anti-acne as Gel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(21): 1447-1467.
90. Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lornoxicam Microsponge-Based Gel as A Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(5): 200-217.
91. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Metronidazole Medicated Chewing Gum Tablets. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(6): 353-370.
92. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Extract for Skin Hyperpigmentation as Gel Advanced Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(22): 1260-1280.
93. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Al Khawlani MA, Yahya TAA. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-acne Spironolactone Emulgel Novel Trend in Topical Drug Delivery System. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(22): 96-119.
94. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Abdullah JH. Lisinopril-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(16): 59-111.
95. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. The Importance of Stability Testing in Pharmaceutical Development of Ceftriaxone Implant Biodegradable Tablets. *Matrix Science Pharma (MSP)*, 2025; 9(2): 58-63.
96. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM. Formulation and Evaluation of Salicylic Acid and Kojic Acid as Gel Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Treatment of Acne and Whitening

- Skin Effect. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 2025; 11(9): 538-548.
97. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024; 13(4): 1408-1423.
98. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Curcuma Longa Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024; 11(6): 37-43.
99. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Simvastatin for the Development of Novel Drug Delivery Systems. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2024; 13(19): 1463-1512.
100. Hamidaddin MA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rosuvastatin Fast Dissolving Tablets. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2023; 12(9): 2293-2303.
101. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Noman MA, Saif AA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rivaroxaban-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 2024; 11(9): 370-404.
102. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Hamidaddin MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Rosuvastatin Calcium-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2024; 13(13): 1549-1582.
103. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. Formulation of Immediate Release Lamotrigine Tablets and Bioequivalence Study. Journal of Chemical Pharm Research, 2013; 5(10): 266-271.
104. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antitumor Activity of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Capsules as Dietary Supplement Herbal Product Against Breast Cancer. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2024; 13(3): 95-114.
105. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Famotidine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2024; 13(18): 1346-1408.

106. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Rubroviolaceae Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 11(4): 53-61.
107. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Famotidine Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023; 10(10): 56-62.
108. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA. Drotaverine-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(18): 1285-1340.
109. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Ticagrelor-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(10): 1081-1132.
110. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Al-Ghorafi MA, Yahya TA, Yassin SH, AlKhawlani MA. Diclofenac-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(14): 1297-1333.
111. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Atorvastatin Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 10(12): 231-236.
112. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Salim YA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Lisinopril Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2023; 12(9): 357-369.
113. Alburyhi MM, Hamidaddin MA, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Rivaroxaban Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(2): 2066-2092.
114. Saif AA, Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies Some Levocetirizine Tablets Brands Available in Sana'a Market Yemen. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(24): 1009-1022.
115. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Aloe Vera Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(8): 1052-1072.
116. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ciprofloxacin Biodegradable Formulations for

- Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023; 10(9): 32-36.
117. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Aboghanem A. Effect of Different Excipients on Formulation of Immediate Release Artemether/Lumefantrine Tablets. *Journal of Chemical Pharm Research*, 2013; 5(11): 617-625.
118. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Dictyota Dichotoma Extract Medicinal Seaweed Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Cancer. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 11(4): 63-70.
119. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Celery Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(11): 2383-2404.
120. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ticagrelor Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(5): 26-55.
121. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yahya TA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Drotaverine Orally Disintegrating Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(18): 66-79.
122. Al-Ghorafi MA, Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Meloxicam-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(1): 87-106.
123. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Effervescent Granules of Artemisia Arborescence Herbal Product for Foodborne Illness. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2023; 12(12): 1429-1444.
124. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Saif RM. Preformulation Study of Ceftriaxone and Ciprofloxacin for Lipid Based Drug Delivery Systems. *EJUA-BA*, 2022; 3(4): 339-350.
125. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Alqubati MA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Clopidogrel Active Ingredient for Orodispersible Tablets Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(3): 996-1015.
126. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Alemad AF. Preformulation Studies of Cefixime for Dispersible Tablets Delivery System Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(12): 75-99.
127. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, AA Saif. Formulation and Evaluation of Meloxicam Emulgel Delivery System for Topical Applications. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(4): 1324-1337.

128. Bary AA, El-Gazayerly ON, Alburyhi MM. A Pharmaceutical Study on Methocarbamol. MSc Thesis, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University, 2006.
129. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saif RM. Recent Innovations of Delivery Systems for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Study of Ceftriaxone Biodegradable Formulations for Post-Operative Infection Prophylaxis. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023; 10(8): 95-99.
130. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Domperidone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(3): 250-269.
131. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Spironolactone-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 14(3): 871-910.
132. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Ketoprofen-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 14(4): 92-123.
133. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Yassin SH. Formulation and Evaluation of Simvastatin Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(16): 1033-1047.
134. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Anti-peptic Ulcer Capsules of Curcuma Longa Herbal Product. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(22): 76-96.
135. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Preformulation and Characterization Studies of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Active Ingredient in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(2): 1603-1620.
136. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Al Ghoury AA. Formulation and Evaluation of Antimalarial Drugs Suppositories. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(20): 89-108.
137. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Saeed SA, Al-Ghorafi MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Diclofenac Orodispersible Tablets. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2023; 10(9): 01-06.
138. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Ketoprofen Fast Dissolving Tablets. *International Journal of Sciences*, 2018; 7(09):27- 39.

139. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Chamomile Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Gout. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(04): 215-228.
140. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA. Metronidazole-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Medicated Chewing Gum Delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(4): 567-589.
141. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Alkhawlan MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Bisoprolol Fast Dissolving Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(16): 01-10.
142. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A, Alwesabi NA. Formulation and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract for Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis as Orodispersible Tablets Delivery System. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(5): 56 -71.
143. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(7): 1264-1282.
144. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(4): 06-13.
145. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA. Evaluation of Vitamin and Mineral Tablets and Capsules in Yemen Market. *Journal of Chemical Pharma Research*, 2013; 5(9):15-26.
146. Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saif AA, Salim YA, Abdullah JH. Formulation and Evaluation of Domperidone Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(3): 49-68.
147. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, Hamidaddin MA. Formulation and Evaluation of Clopidogrel Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(6): 42-64.
148. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, AlKhawlan MA. Bisoprolol-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 10(10): 304-324.

149. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Hepatoprotective. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(8): 1309-1334.
150. Saif AA, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Abudunia A. Amoxicillin-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Advanced Drug delivery Systems Development. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(6): 530-562.
151. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Pharmaceutical Solution of Pandanus Odoratissimus L Extract Herbal Product in Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(1): 1840-1851.
152. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation and Evaluation of Antibacterial Orodispersible Tablets of Artemisia Arborescence Extract Herbal Product. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2024; 11(2): 409-417.
153. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Acalypha Fruticosa Extract Tablets Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(8): 1073-1091.
154. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA, Abdullah JH, Yahya TAA. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Amlodipine and Furosemide Orodispersible Tablets. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(5): 358-378.
155. Alburyhi MM, Mohamed YAS, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Amlodipine for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(11): 95-136.
156. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies with Pharmaceutical Excipients of Clopidogrel for the Development of Novel Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(06): 1448-1486.
157. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Ginger Extract Capsules Delivery System as an Advanced Phytotherapy Approach for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 11(6): 400-415.
158. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA. Evaluation and Drug Stability Studies of Different Brands of Clopidogrel Tablets Available in Sana'a City Market, Yemen. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2025; 12(7): 181-191.

159. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA, AlGhoury ABA. Compatibility Studies of Chloroquine Phosphate with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2025; 14(14): 1325-1360.
160. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Plicosepalus Acacia Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Controlling Diabetes. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 2025; 11(6): 323-337.
161. Saif AA, Abdullah JH, Alburyhi MM, Noman MA, Saeed SA. Sildenafil-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Pharmaceutical Oral Suspensions Advanced Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2026; 15(6): 869-908.
162. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Recent Innovations of Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Pandanus Odoratissimus Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical for Breast Cancer. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2024; 13(8): 1092-1112.
163. Alburyhi MM, El-Shaibany A. Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Tribulus Terrestris Extract Capsules as Naturaceutical Novel Drug Delivery Systems for Kidney Stones. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2024; 13(5): 1425-1443.
164. Alburyhi MM, Saif AA, Noman MA. Compatibility Studies of Pyrimethamine with Pharmaceutical Excipients for the Development of Suppositories Novel Drug Delivery Systems. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 2025; 12(9): 394-412.
165. Alburyhi MM, Yahya TAA, Saif AA, Noman MA, Alshoba N, Saeed SA. Acyclovir-Excipient Compatibility Studies for Gel Novel Drug Delivery Systems Development. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2026; 15(6): 1247-1292.
166. Prathyusha CH, Murthy TEGK. Compatibility Studies of Donepezil with Different Excipients by Using HPLC and FTIR. *J Adv Pharm Tech Res*, 2013; 3:273-278.
167. Jangde R, Singh D. Compatibility Studies of Quercetin with Pharmaceutical Excipients used in The Development of Novel Formulation. *Research J Pharm and Tech*, 2014; 7: 1101-1105.
168. Shirwaikar AC. Galan Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Famotidine by Dry Granulation Method. *Ind J Pharm Sci.*, 2004; 66: 422-426.

169. Chauhan I, Yasir M, Verma M, Singh AP. Nanostructured Lipid Carriers: A Groundbreaking Approach for Transdermal Drug Delivery. *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 2020; 10(2): 150.